

FOOD IMAGE RECOGNITION AND CALORIE PREDICTION USING CNN

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Abstract—This paper introduces an innovative approach for monitoring nutritional intake through the utilization of image detection and deep learning methodologies. The proposed system employs computer vision and Convolutional Neural Network (CNNs) to predict the calorie content of food item from images. To further enhance its utility, the system incorporates logistic regression, utilizing user input such as height, weight, age, and gender to predict whether the identified food items are suitable for the individual's dietary requirements. Through extensive training on a dataset comprising 700 images across different food categories, and commendable accuracy of 89.16% was achieved. Accessible via a user-friendly webpage interface, the deployed system enables individuals to upload images of their meals, facilitating real-time identification of food items alongside their estimated calorie counts. This technology offers a practical and reliable means of tracking dietary habits, particularly beneficial for those striving to maintain a healthy lifestyle or manage their weight effectively. By providing insights into the nutritional composition of various foods, the system empowers users to make informed decisions regarding their dietary choices.

Keywords—Image Detection, CNN, Calorie estimation, Logistic Regression

I. INTRODUCTION

1. With the advancement of technology, there's a growing awareness among people regarding their dietary choices, driven by the prevalent issue of obesity. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the global prevalence of overweight individuals, including obesity, is alarming. In 2016, approximately 1.9 billion adults and 40 million children under 5 years old were reported overweight. Fast food and junk food consumption among youth is on the rise due to influences like western lifestyle and media advertisements, leading to various chronic diseases such as heart problems, diabetes, and kidney damage. To address these concerns, food journaling has gained popularity as a means to monitor calorie intake digitally using smartphones or cameras. However, accurately detecting food items and estimating their calorie content poses challenges due to the wide variety of cuisines and food images worldwide. Despite years of research, existing systems struggle with low accuracy in food detection and calorie estimation.

Motivated by the escalating concern surrounding dietary habits and the prevalence of obesity, we embarked on an extensive research endeavor. Our focus was on developing a robust system capable of accurately identifying food items

from images and providing corresponding calorie estimations. The proposed model centers on leveraging Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture for food detection. Our methodology involved constructing a dataset comprising different food categories. Subsequently, we trained the model utilizing CNN and deployed it on a webpage for real-time result display. Upon inputting an image, the system promptly predicts the identified food item along with its estimated calorie content. This research endeavor represents a significant stride towards addressing the challenges associated with food detection and calorie estimation, offering a promising avenue for digital food journaling and nutritional tracking.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Advancements in the field of food detection and calorie estimation continue to evolve rapidly, with ongoing contributions pushing the boundaries of capability. Here, we summarize key insights gleaned from our exploration:

Ayon et al. [1] proposed a comprehensive system for food detection and calorie estimation utilizing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Their system comprises two distinct CNN models: one for food detection and another for calorie estimation. Initially, the food detection model identifies the presence of food in input images, while the calorie estimation model subsequently estimates the calorie content of the detected food item. Training and evaluation were conducted on a dataset of food images with ground truth calorie information, resulting in high accuracy for both food detection and calorie estimation. The authors highlight the potential applications of their system in health and nutrition, particularly in areas such as dietary monitoring and meal planning. Notably, the method demonstrated a success rate of approximately 89.48% accuracy, validating its effectiveness in practical scenarios.

In Subhi et al. 2018 research paper [2] introduced a model centered on the CNN algorithm, designed to identify food items. Their study utilized a novel dataset comprising local Malaysian cuisine, featuring eleven food categories and totaling 5800 images. The authors employed two distinct datasets in their methodology: the FOOD-101 dataset for food/non-food classification and their proprietary Malaysian food dataset for food categorization. Notably, they emphasized the extensive utilization of convolutional networks, boasting 24 weight layers, to achieve robust food image classification. Their proposed model adopted a complex architecture comprising multiple convolutional layers preceding the final fully connected layer. Through their experiments, Subhi et al. underscored the importance of network depth in enhancing the efficacy of visual representations during training.

Kasyap et al. [3] introduced a system focusing on food calorie estimation utilizing a CNN architecture. Their system takes food images as input and employs a CNN to predict the calorie count of the depicted food item. The authors conducted training and evaluation using a dataset of food images with known calorie information, achieving promising outcomes with an average error rate of 14.8%. With potential applications in healthcare, nutrition, and fitness domains, the system demonstrates versatility and practical utility. The method's effectiveness was validated with an impressive accuracy rate of approximately 97%, highlighting its reliability and suitability for real-world implementation.

Using supervised learning approaches, Manal Chokr and Shady Elbassuoni (2017)[4] provided a solution for single meal classification and calorie prediction. Their method uses a model that receives an image of a food item as input and outputs an estimate of its calories. They created a Mathwork Image Process program to extract features from the food photographs in order to accomplish this. After extraction, these features are compressed and sent into a regressor and classifier. The food item's size is determined by the regressor, and the food item's kind is identified by the classifier. The classifier and regressor's outputs are then passed into a second regressor, which yields the final result of calorie estimation.

Zhang et al. [5] introduced a system aimed at food calorie estimation, employing various machine learning models. The authors conducted a comparative analysis of four distinct machine learning models: linear regression, k-nearest neighbors, support vector regression, and random forest. This analysis was performed on a dataset of food images accompanied by ground truth calorie information. The findings revealed that the random forest model outperformed the others, achieving the lowest average error rate of 21.9%. The system demonstrates potential applications in healthcare, nutrition, and fitness domains, underscoring its relevance and versatility in practical settings.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Fig.1

A. Dataset Collection

The dataset consists of five distinct food items: Pizza, Burger, Chicken Tikka, Soup, and Rice. Images of these items were sourced from various sources on the internet. Before training the system, it was ensured that the correct photos were present in each of the food groups.

The Calorie dataset incorporates features such as height, weight, age, gender, calorie content.

B. Dataset sample

2. A total of 5 different food categories were utilized for the datasets, with each cuisine class containing 100 photos. Presenting a high-quality sample from the database posed a bit of a challenge. Nonetheless, the dataset encompassed a comprehensive range of foods commonly consumed by people. Utilizing the calorie.csv dataset, alongside logistic regression, the system predicts whether a food item is suitable for consumption based on user characteristics, empowering informed dietary decisions.

C. Data Preprocessing

For training the model to classify images into five distinct classes, a series of specific steps were followed. Essential libraries such as os, cv2, numpy, and sklearn were imported to handle data preprocessing and model development. Following this, constants, including image size, batch size, epochs, and the number of classes, were defined. A function named 'load_data' was implemented to load and preprocess the dataset, which involved traversing through the dataset directory, reading each image via OpenCV, resizing them to a standardized size of 128x128 pixels, and assigning labels to each image. The facilitated organization, and images were segregated into training and testing sets using a 80-20 split.

This proposed system utilizes data preprocessing and logistic regression to predict food suitability based on user characteristics using the Calorie.csv dataset. After encoding gender and splitting the data, logistic regression is trained and evaluated for accuracy. Upon receiving user input, the model predicts calorie intake, enabling real-time assessment. By comparing predicted intake with a predefined threshold, personalized recommendations are provided, facilitating informed dietary decisions and promoting healthier lifestyles

D. Feature Extraction Technique

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are used in this suggested system's tiered approach to abstract features. In the beginning, learnable filters are applied to convolutional layers, which scan input images to extract features like edges and textures. The network is then made nonlinear by applying the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. Then, to downsample the feature maps while keeping important information, max-pooling layers are used.

As the process progresses through multiple convolutional and pooling layers, the resultant feature maps are flattened into one-dimensional vectors via the Flatten operation. This step readies the features for input into fully connected layers, which are responsible for classification based on the extracted features. This systematic procedure enables the CNN to automatically discern relevant features from input images and proficiently classify them into distinct classes.

This proposed system also for predicting calorie intake based on user characteristics, employing logistic regression. Initially, the gender column is encoded using LabelEncoder for logistic regression compatibility. Subsequently, the dataset is divided into features (height, weight, age, and gender) and target variables (calorie intake). Following data

splitting into training and testing sets, a logistic regression model is trained and evaluated for accuracy. Upon receiving user input, the model predicts calorie intake, facilitating real-time assessment and personalized dietary recommendations. This feature abstraction approach underscores the significance of logistic regression in nutritional research and personalized healthcare management.

IV. BUILD THE MODEL

The initial step in food calorie detection involves constructing the model, which serves as the primary phase. During this stage, the user employs various algorithms to develop the model. The actions required during model construction include:

A. Import the necessary libraries

```
import streamlit as st
import numpy as np
from PIL import Image
import os
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
```

Fig.2

B. Set data for train, validation and test image and calorie datasets

```
def load_data(data_dir):
    images = []
    labels = []
    class_names = os.listdir(data_dir)
    for i, class_name in enumerate(class_names):
        class_dir = os.path.join(data_dir, class_name)
        for image_name in os.listdir(class_dir):
            image_path = os.path.join(class_dir, image_name)
            image = cv2.imread(image_path)
            image = cv2.resize(image, IMAGE_SIZE)
            images.append(image)
            label = np.zeros(NUM_CLASSES, dtype=int) # Initialize label as an array of zeros
            label[i] = 1 # Set the index corresponding to the class to 1
            labels.append(label)
    return np.array(images), np.array(labels)

# Load and preprocess the dataset
data_dir = 'dataset' # Directory containing pizza, burger, and soup images
images, labels = load_data(data_dir)

# Split data into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(images, labels, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

data = pd.read_csv('Calorie.csv')
label_encoder = LabelEncoder()
data['gender'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(data['gender'])
if gender == "Male":
    gen=1
else:
    gen=0
X = data[['height', 'weight', 'age', 'gender']]
y = data['calorie']
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

model.fit(
    X_train / 255.0,
    y_train,
    batch_size=BATCH_SIZE,
    epochs=EPOCHS,
    validation_data=(X_test / 255.0, y_test))
```

Fig.5

Fig.4

C. Train the models

```
model = LogisticRegression()
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

Fig.6

D. Evaluating the accuracy

```
loss, accuracy = model.evaluate(X_test / 255.0, y_test)
st.write("Test Loss:", loss)
st.write("Test Accuracy:", accuracy)
```

Fig.7

V. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

This study's main goal is to identify the number of calories in food items that are pictured so that people can fight against diseases including diabetes, obesity, heart disease, and kidney failure—all of which are linked to being overweight. Understanding the calories in food gives people the power to control their calorie consumption and live better lives.

Fig.8

VI. REFERENCES

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